

Food, Health and Environment Research Infrastructures to Tackle Emerging Priorities

Deliverable 5.2 Strategic technology and service needs

TECHNICAL REFERENCES

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GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

FHERITALE Identification and extraction of strategic technology and service needs

FHERITALE addresses the growing scientific, technological and societal challenges associated with artificial materials - such as micro- and nanoplastics, bioplastics, plastic additives and metallic particles - across food systems, human health and the environment. These challenges are inherently cross-domain and require coordinated access to advanced analytical services, interoperable data infrastructures and harmonised methodologies. Based on 815 scientific articles and outcomes from EU projects, we identified strategic technology and service needs by taking advantage of state-of-the-art AI technologies. The approach automatically extracted and classified cited micro- and nanoplastic-related needs from documents covering priority domains such as environment, food, & health

KEY NEEDS: The thematic analysis highlights key priority areas for advancing research and management of micro- and nanoplastics. Major needs include **improved detection of smaller particles, optimized analytical workflows, the development of harmonized methods and realistic reference materials** to ensure data comparability. Strong emphasis is also placed on **environmental monitoring** and modelling of particle fate, as well as more ecologically relevant impact assessments. In human health, **understanding toxicokinetics** and leveraging **advanced in vitro and omics approaches** are critical. Regulatory progress requires **MNP-specific risk assessment frameworks** and standardized thresholds, while growing data complexity calls for **advanced modelling and AI-based tools**. Finally, the development of sustainable alternatives and improved wastewater treatment solutions remains essential for **effective mitigation and prevention**.

1. Executive summary

Deliverable 5.2 (D5.2) contributes to **WP5 Task 5.2** of **FHERITALE**, which focuses on turning key scientific and policy ambitions into practical services that research infrastructures (RIs) can provide, and identifying what technologies are needed to support research on micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) in the areas of food, health, and the environment. The report presents a compilation of current and emerging technological needs related to MNPs, including their detection, analysis, environmental fate, and impacts on human and ecological health.

WP5 is located at the intersection of analytical service mapping (WP3) and thematic prioritization (WP4), and acts as a bridge toward gap analysis (WP6) and the development of coordinated strategies for future services (WP7 and WP8) in the domain of MNP research. It supports FHERITALE's overarching goal of creating a cohesive and service-oriented research infrastructure landscape capable of responding to the evolving challenges posed by artificial materials, especially MNPs.

D5.2 contributes directly to the identification of technology gaps and priority needs, in alignment with Objective 3 (O3) of FHERITALE, which focuses on identifying service gaps, technological needs, and research and technology (R&T) priorities that address high-impact scientific challenges. By doing so, D5.2 helps lay the foundation for co-creating a roadmap for future service development within FHERITALE.

2. Introduction

D5.2 aims to identify and structure technological needs and gaps from recent scientific literature (2020-2025) addressing key selected priorities defined in WP4 including “Micro and nanoplastics (MNPs)”, “Bioplastics”, “Plastic additives”, “Metals/Metal oxides”, in the context (domain) of food, health, and the environment. The focus was placed on challenges and unmet requirements described or implied by the authors of the scientific literature.

To address this, a mixed-method approach was adopted (discussed in section 3 Methodology). This approach involved an initial information extraction step combined with a systematic literature review, structured data handling and manual analysis. Source materials included over 800 peer-reviewed articles, EU-funded project outputs, and reports from the European Commission (EC) publications, the Joint Research Centre (JRC), the European Environment Agency (EEA), the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA), the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) and the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) technical norms as well as documents from umbrella industry groups.

AI-supported extraction tools were selected, following EU guidelines [1] on their use and applications, to efficiently screen large volumes of literature and identify relevant technological needs from literature using purpose-designed prompts. This method is particularly suited for handling the scale and heterogeneity of the various sources, as demonstrated in studies employing AI for systematic reviews and evidence synthesis [2,3]. Manual review of extracted outputs confirmed the validity of this method. Technological needs were then assigned to

thematic groups based on content and relevance and subsequently classified into sub-thematics via a validated AI classification algorithm which permits to quantify the frequency of cited requirement and gaps and identify the leading needs in this desk research analysis.

3. Methodology

3.1. Identification of Technology Needs

This section presents the methodological framework used to identify and extract technological needs related to MNPs. The objective aimed to generate a systematic and high-coverage synthesis of gaps across research, policy, and applied domains relevant to MNPs. As illustrated in Figure 1, the methodology consisted of three core elements.

Figure 1 : Methodology for identifying the technology needs

3.1.1. Source Identification and Literature Selection

To ensure a comprehensive and relevant dataset, literature and reports were selected from the following sources:

- I. **Peer-reviewed scientific** articles identified in the FHERITALE article database [4]. This curated database includes 813 original research articles focused on MNPs, bioplastics, metals/metal oxides, and plastic additives. Articles are categorized by material type, particle size, and research technique, covering domains such as spectroscopy, mass spectrometry, omics, microscopy, and biological assessments. It was developed using structured search queries on Web of Science™ and is publicly available via Zenodo.
- II. **EU policy and scientific documents**, including:
 - The EC reports and regulations addressing chemical safety, microplastic pollution, and nanoplastics, such as the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability, the state of knowledge on nanoplastics, EU action against microplastics, and Commission Regulation (EU) 2023/2055 (L 238/67) [5–8].

- The EFSA assessment on the presence of microplastics and nanoplastics in food, with a focus on seafood [9].
 - The EEA publications on biodegradable plastics, plastic releases in the EU, circular economy strategies, and the transformation of Europe’s food system [10–13].
 - The JRC stakeholder survey on the material needs related to microplastics [14].
 - The ECHA reports on nanomaterials and their implications, including reproductive toxicity, dermal absorption, biodegradation, and regulatory innovation [15–18].
 - ISO standards and technical reports relevant to plastics and nanomaterials [19–22].
- III. **EU-funded project deliverables** related to micro- and nanoplastics (e.g., Horizon Europe and H2020 projects, with particular attention to outcomes from the CUSP cluster of projects on micro- and nanoplastics, and prioritization frameworks such as those developed by COST-PRIORITY and COST-ICPLASTIC) (see Table 1). EU-funded projects were selected from targeted CORDIS research and the PlasticHeal database, an extensive repository of plastic-related projects, to support the identification of technological needs [23].

The project selection was done according to the following selection criteria:

- Projects had to focus on Europe and operate at an international or multi-country level.
- They were required to explicitly address micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs).
- Projects completed before 2020 were excluded to ensure relevance to current challenges.
- Associated documents had to be accessible through official platforms such as CORDIS, OpenAIRE, Zenodo, or the EC’s website.
- Only projects producing broad-scope outputs such as deliverables, policy briefs, or advisory reports were retained.

This ensured that the projects reviewed had a clear European relevance, addressed current challenges, and provided publicly available, actionable content suitable for extracting technological needs.

These criteria led to the identification of 25 EU projects that were relevant for further investigation. The selected projects included are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 : Selected EU project addressing MNPs

Project Title	Description
AURORA	Investigates the exposure and health impacts of MNPs during pregnancy and early life, aiming to develop a European roadmap for early-life health risk assessment of MNPs.
CLAIM	Develops innovative technologies to prevent and manage marine plastic pollution, aiming to reduce macro and microplastics in European seas.
COST - PRIORITY	COST Action PRIORITY is a science and technology research network focused on developing, implementing, and consolidating strategies to tackle the global challenges of micro- and nanoplastics in the environment.

CUSP	A consortium of five research initiatives focusing on understanding the health impacts of micro- and nanoplastics, bringing together 75 organizations from 21 countries.
DECOMPOSE	Aimed to develop biodegradable commodity plastics using metallocsupramolecular polymers derived from renewable resources.
EUROqCHARM	Aims to analyse and harmonize existing methodologies for plastic pollution assessment and monitoring across Europe.
FlexFunction2Sustain	Creates an Open Innovation Test Bed for nano-functionalization technologies, enabling sustainable and smart plastics and paper-based products.
IMPTOX	Develops an analytical platform to investigate the effects and toxicity of micro- and nanoplastics combined with environmental contaminants on the risk of allergic diseases.
i-plastic / JPI Oceans	Assesses the dispersion and impacts of micro- and nanoplastics in tropical and temperate oceans.
LABPLAS	Develops new methods to detect microplastics at sea, aiming to improve monitoring and assessment of plastic pollution in marine environments.
microplastiX	Investigates the degradation mechanisms of microplastics in environmental conditions to understand how weathering affects plastic materials.
MINAGRIS	Assesses the impact of plastic debris in agricultural soils on biodiversity, plant productivity, and ecosystem services.
MONPLAS	Trains early-stage researchers to develop technologies for monitoring concentrations of micro- and nanoplastics in water.
PAPILLONS	Studies the sources, behaviour, and ecological effects of micro- and nanoplastics in agricultural soils.
PLASTICHEAL	Develops innovative tools to study the impact and mode of action of micro- and nanoplastics on human health.
PlasticsFatE	Aims to enhance understanding of the impact of micro- and nanoplastics on human health by investigating exposure pathways.
Plastisol	Defines indicators for the presence of microplastics in soils by considering various transformation and degradation stages.
Plasttrack	Develops a methodological toolbox to track the degradation pathways of plastics in the environment.
RECOVER	Develops biotechnological solutions using microorganisms, enzymes, earthworms, and insects to degrade conventional plastics.
SOPLAS	A multi-disciplinary training network focusing on macro- and microplastics in agricultural soils.
MOMENTUM	A Dutch research consortium investigating the health effects of MNPs on humans.
POLYRISK	Explores human exposure to micro- and nanoplastics, particularly their potential immunotoxic effects.
COST-ICPLASTIC	COST Action ICPLASTIC is developing ISO-compatible, efficient, and reproducible protocols and equipment for micro- and nanoplastic detection.
PlasticTrace	Develops metrological tools and reference materials to detect and quantify micro- and nanoplastics in food and environmental samples.

LimnoPlast	Addresses microplastics in European freshwater ecosystems through interdisciplinary research.
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- IV. **Umbrella industry group documents** are relevant for identifying technology needs related to MNPs, as their strategic documents highlight implementation-level constraints across production, recycling, standardisation, and regulatory compliance. These sources reveal translational bottlenecks affecting large-scale deployment and policy alignment. The selected Industry groups are listed in Table 2.

Table 2 : Selected Industry groups

Industry Group	Description
Cefic (European Chemical Industry Council)	Represents the EU chemical industry; advocates science-based policy, sustainable biomass use, and regulatory clarity for bio-based plastics.
Ellen MacArthur Foundation	Promotes systemic transition to a circular economy, including EPR schemes, packaging redesign, and elimination of problematic plastics.
EuRIC (European Recycling Industries' Confederation)	Represents EU recyclers; advocates traceable recycled content rules, fair trade conditions, and stronger EU recycling markets.
FoodDrinkEurope	Represents EU food and drink manufacturers; supports circular packaging while ensuring food safety and supply chain functionality.
PlasticsEurope	Represents European plastics producers; promotes circular plastics, recycling expansion, and industry input to the Global Plastics Treaty.
Plastics Pact Network	Multi-stakeholder platform accelerating national and global circular plastics commitments aligned with a Global Plastics Treaty.
SusChem (European Technology Platform for Sustainable Chemistry)	Drives innovation in sustainable chemistry, advanced recycling, and bio-based plastics through industry–research collaboration.

3.1.2. Methodology for Literature Review and Extraction of Technological Needs

To ensure consistent and scalable identification of technological needs across a broad and diverse set of sources, artificial intelligence tools, in strict adherence with EU guidelines and practice, were used to support the review process. This allowed for systematic extraction of specific insights related to methodological gaps, limitations, and innovation needs, while keeping a clear link to each original source.

The process combined two complementary approaches:

- Assisted extraction of the EU documents using ChatGPT-4.0, prompted with the following instruction:

“You are analysing scientific articles for actionable insights. Your task is to extract and present only the TECHNOLOGICAL NEEDS discussed or implied in each article. Avoid general research summaries.

For each article, extract the following fields:

1. Name: The file name or source ID.
2. Title: The full title of the scientific article.
3. DOI: Digital Object Identifier (if available).
4. Category: A thematic label for the type of technological need.
5. Need: A concise, clear, and specific TECHNOLOGICAL NEED or GAP. This should describe what needs to be developed, improved, or replaced technologically (tools, models, systems, processes, etc.).
6. Details: Provide supporting information that explains or contextualizes the need why existing methods are insufficient, and what the proposed or implied innovation addresses.

Do: Focus on methods, tools, models, or applications mentioned as inadequate or needing development. Group similar needs under thematic categories if working with multiple documents. Maintain traceability to each article using the file name or DOI.

Do Not: Do not summarize the article. Do not restate conclusions unless they highlight a technological limitation. Do not list general research goals. Do not list need for equipment.”

- Due to the high volume of the literature used for review (>800 articles), the manual use of ChatGPT-4.0 was not feasible for full information/data extraction. Instead, the AI-based tool SciSpace was employed to extract technological needs from the literature using varied prompts (e.g. Gap(s), need(s), limitation(s); Technology improvements; Techniques limitations and combination of these keywords) designed to maximize the retrieval of relevant information. These prompts focused on identifying methodological gaps, analytical limitations, and tool development needs.

Following automated extraction with SciSpace, a manual screening of the results was conducted to retain only technological needs based on human judgement. To validate the reliability of this approach, a manual extraction of needs from a randomized sample of 10 scientific articles was performed and compared with the SciSpace output (see Supplementary material). The results showed that SciSpace did not overlook any relevant needs found manually, and the tool consistently identified more relevant needs than the manual method, demonstrating its value for large-scale, high-coverage extraction.

3.2. Thematic Grouping of Needs

3.2.1. Classification of needs into thematic groups and domains

To support structured analysis, all extracted technological needs were grouped into eight thematic groups, as shown in Table 3. The resulting datasets were structured as follows:

- The dataset is structured with the following fields: EU Project/ institutions, Title of the source document, DOI or Identifier, Technological Need, Details/Context, Assigned Category, and domain.
- The thematic groups were developed based on the types of needs most frequently identified in the reviewed literature and documents and domain were based on the project thematic. This approach allowed for consistent classification and presentation.

Table 3 : Defined thematic groups and domains

Thematic Groups
Analytical Methods & Detection Technologies
Standardization & Reference Materials
Data & Digital Tools
Exposure, Monitoring & Fate
Ecotoxicology & Environment
Human Health & Toxicology
Regulation, Policy & Risk Assessment
Circular Economy, Sustainability & Safe-by-Design
Domains
Food
Health
Environment
Cross-domain

3.2.2. Classification of needs into thematic sub-groups

To enable a more granular and quantitative analysis, all extracted needs were subsequently classified into thematic sub-groups within each main thematic group. This second-level classification was designed to capture conceptual and functional similarities between needs, reduce heterogeneity within thematic groups, and allow a refined quantification of needs beyond high-level domain counts.

This step was performed using automated classification of previously extracted need into predefined thematic sub-groups based on literature search. The automated classification has been performed using GPT4o accessed via the OpenAi API, which was prompted with the extracted need statements and the thematic sub-group defined in section 4.2.

This has been prompted with the following instructions :

- "You receive short service or technology needs related to micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs).\n",
- "Assign EACH need to exactly ONE of the following thematic classes:\n\n"
- *Insertion of extracted needs* (Cf. section 4.2.,
- Table 4)
- "\n\nReturn ONLY strict JSON with keys:\n",

- "{ \"need\": <string>, \"class\": <one of the classes exactly as written above> }.\n"

The model evaluated semantic similarity and contextual relevance to determine the most appropriate sub-group assignment for each need. This approach ensured consistency across a large number of heterogeneous textual inputs (individual needs). Following automated classification, assignments were subject to expert validation. A random sample of 100 extracted needs has been assessed in order to validate the classification.

4. Results

4.1. Identified Technology Needs

This section provides an overview of the key technological needs identified in relation to MNPs. It draws on extensive analysis of policy, regulatory, and scientific documents issued by the EC, EFSA, EEA, ECHA, JRC, ISO (see section 3.1.1). Additionally, this integrates findings from a wide range of EU-funded research projects and initiatives (see Table 1), as well as recent scientific literature on the broad topic of MNPs. The analysis is structured into eight thematic sections reflecting critical domains in MNPs research and management. The following sections expand on each of these groups in detail, providing source-referenced descriptions of the specific needs identified. The quantitative analysis extracted a total of 385 technological needs from EU-funded sources and 903 technological needs from the scientific literature. Figure 2 presents an overview of the technological needs distribution by thematic groups. All detailed results, including breakdowns by source and category, are available in Supplementary material.

The pie chart highlights the relative importance of each domain in terms of identified technological needs. The largest proportion falls under "Analytical Methods & Detection Technologies," indicating a strong emphasis across sources on the need to improve detection sensitivity, resolution, and quantification methods for MNPs. This is followed by "Standardization & Reference Materials" and "Circular Economy, Sustainability & Safe-by-Design," underscoring current gaps in harmonized protocols and sustainable material innovation. Thematic groups such as "Exposure, Monitoring & Fate" and "Human Health & Toxicology" also feature prominently, reflecting ongoing concern about the pathways, transformation, and health impacts of MNPs. "Data and Digital Tools," "Ecotoxicology & Environment," and "Regulation, Policy & Risk Assessment" are comparatively less represented, although they remain essential to comprehensive MNPs management. The distribution reveals both current research strengths and areas requiring further attention. Figure 3 presents the distribution of the needs by domains. This distribution reflects the proportion of identified needs according to the domain focus of the document from which they were extracted. Most needs originate from cross-domain and environment-focused studies. Health-focused studies and food-specific studies account for a smaller share.

Figure 2 : Identified technology needs by thematic groups

Figure 3 : Identified technology needs by domains

4.2. Identified thematic sub-groups of technology needs

The sections below present a summary of the identified technological needs, grouped into eight thematic groups. Each subsection (sub-groups) combines findings from EU-funded projects, scientific literature and industry groups papers, with source references provided. This structure allows for a focused overview of priority areas across MNPs research and management.

Table 4 lists all thematic sub-groups identified.

Table 4 : Identified thematic sub-groups

Thematic group	Thematic sub-group
Analytical Methods & Detection Technologies	Detection of Smaller Particles and Improved Sensitivity Advanced Spectroscopic and Imaging Techniques High-Throughput and Untargeted Analytical Workflows Optimization of Sample Preparation and Digestion Protocols Raman-Based Detection: Substrate and Laser Optimization Integrated and Multi-Modal Analytical Approaches Addressing Instrumental Limitations and Background Noise Accurate Quantification and Mass Conversion Advanced Imaging for Biological Studies Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) Optimization Microfluidic and Sensor Platforms Instrument-Specific Hardware Improvements Portable Devices and Software for Real-Time Sensing
Standardization and Reference Materials	Harmonized Methods and Protocols Reference Materials and Realistic Models Regulatory Relevance and Remaining Gaps
Data & Digital Tools	Integrated Detection and Analytical Platforms AI and Machine Learning for Classification and Interpretation Data Harmonization and Knowledge Integration Digital Platforms for Policy and Ecosystem Integration Behavioural and Socioeconomic Modelling Tools Advanced Modelling, Simulation and Bioinformatics Tools Statistical and Chemometric Support
Exposure, Monitoring & Fate Analysis	Monitoring Human and Environmental Exposure Environmental Monitoring and Sampling Tools Degradation, Fate, and Transport Modelling Dosimetry and Biomonitoring for Exposure Quantification Chronic Exposure and Mixture Toxicity Models Agricultural and Ecosystem Impacts
Ecotoxicology & Environment	Hazard Assessment Under Realistic Environmental Conditions Risks of Biodegradable Plastics and Additives Monitoring of Impacts on Soil Health and Ecosystem Function Microbial and Pathogen-Related Risks Molecular and Organism-Level Responses Combined Effects and Environmental Interactions

	Agricultural Productivity and Ecosystem Resilience
Human Health & Toxicology	Toxicokinetic and Systemic Health Impacts Development of Realistic and Ethical Toxicity Models Advanced In Vitro and Omics-Based Tools Cellular and Molecular Toxicity Endpoints Health Impacts of Weathered and Realistic MNPs MNPs as Vectors for Contaminants and Pathogens Extended Toxicological Targets and Systems Biology
Regulation, Policy & Risk Assessment	Gaps in Regulatory Frameworks and Mixture Assessment Risk Assessment Tools Tailored to MNPs Policy Integration for Circularity and Sustainable Design Standardization in Regulatory Testing and Thresholds Economic and Market Instruments for Risk Mitigation Integration into International Standards and Policy Instruments Monitoring, Infrastructure and Enforcement Technologies Advanced Modelling and Decision Support Tools
Circular Economy, Sustainability & Safe-by-Design	Development of Sustainable and Biodegradable Alternatives Safe-by-Design and Functional Innovation Recycling, Reprocessing, and Circular Economy Integration Reducing Unintentional Emissions via Product Design Biotechnology and Plastic Degradation Labelling, Traceability, and Consumer Communication Food System Applications and Intelligent Materials Advancements in Wastewater Treatment and Capture Material Engineering and Composite Innovation Enzymatic and Photocatalytic Degradation Pathways Agricultural Applications and Mulching Films Environmental Remediation and Recovery Technologies Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) in Food and Agriculture

4.2.1. Analytical Methods & Detection Technologies

Accurately detecting and characterizing MNPs remains one of the most pressing challenges in the field. Analytical limitations stem from the small size, compositional diversity, and complex environmental or biological matrices in which MNPs are found. Despite growing awareness and investment, current methods often lack the sensitivity, specificity, and standardization necessary for reliable detection, particularly at the nanoscale-levels. This section outlines key technological needs identified across European research initiatives and scientific literature, focusing on advancements in particle detection, spectroscopic resolution, analytical throughput, and sample processing.

4.2.1.1. *Detection of Smaller Particles and Improved Sensitivity*

Accurately detecting nanoplastics <1 µm is a persistent technological challenge. Numerous studies highlight the need for more sensitive and precise detection methods, especially for

particles at the nanoscale level. For instance, PlasticHeal calls for the development of Confocal Raman Microscopy (CRM) techniques capable of detecting particles down to 50 nm in biological matrices [24]. Similarly, PlasticsFatE identified the need for advanced analytical methods to isolate and quantify nanoscale particles in soils [25]. Further literature supports enhanced sensitivity and detection capabilities for particles under 100 nm [26,27] as well as sub-50 nm detection in complex matrices like food, water, and tissues [28–30].

4.2.1.2. Advanced Spectroscopic and Imaging Techniques

Standard infrared (IR) and Raman spectroscopy techniques often fall short when analysing degraded, highly fragmented, or small-sized plastic particles. To address these limitations, alternative and enhanced imaging techniques are being developed. The AURORA project promotes two-photon spectroscopy as a promising alternative for characterizing aged and fragmented MNPs [31]. Additional advances include hyperspectral stimulated Raman scattering (SRS) imaging [32], optical photothermal infrared (O-PTIR) microspectroscopy [33], and photothermal-induced resonance (PTIR) spectroscopy [34]. Researchers are also exploring scanning transmission X-ray microscopy (STXM) for structural characterization [35], and enhancements to ATR-FTIR and micro-Raman imaging to improve resolution and minimize fluorescence interference [36,37].

4.2.1.3. High-Throughput and Untargeted Analytical Workflows

Traditional targeted analytical techniques often fail to capture the diversity of micro- and nanoplastic particles and their co-contaminants. As a response, projects such as AURORA have developed high-throughput workflows using LC- and GC-HRMS to enable more comprehensive assessments of both particles and associated chemicals [38]. In parallel, pyrolysis-GC-MS and thermal desorption-based techniques have been highlighted as critical tools for analysing complex environmental and biological matrices with minimal sample preparation. These methods support accurate quantification of micro- and nanoplastics in tissues, sediments, and food, with growing emphasis on improving their detection thresholds and throughput [39,40]. Building on thermal desorption principles, thermal desorption–proton-transfer-reaction mass spectrometry (TD-PTR-MS) offers high sensitivity, minimal sample requirements, and effective fingerprinting of polymers in complex matrices. Its further development could significantly enhance untargeted, high-throughput workflows for micro- and nanoplastics [41].

4.2.1.4. Optimization of Sample Preparation and Digestion Protocols

Sample preparation is a key determinant of analytical accuracy in MNPs detection, as inappropriate digestion or extraction steps can introduce artefacts or degrade plastic particles. For example, PlasticHeal reported interference caused by high background levels in digested food samples such as milk, calling for improved enzymatic and chemical digestion workflows [24]. AURORA also noted solubility artifacts and thermal limitations when analysing certain polymers like PE, PP, and PVC (AURORA - Protocols of high-throughput analysis) [38]. Scientific studies stress the need for optimized pre-treatment methods, including ultrafiltration, hydrogen peroxide digestion, and KOH treatment, tailored to preserve particle integrity across various matrices such as seafood, water, and biota [27,42,43].

4.2.1.5. Raman-Based Detection: Substrate and Laser Optimization

Raman spectroscopy is widely used for MNP identification but suffers from sensitivity issues due to substrate interference and fluorescence. To overcome these limitations, PlasticHeal proposed substrate upgrades such as quartz, calcium fluoride (CaF₂), or silicon wafers to minimize photoluminescence, and laser tuning to avoid sample burning [44]. Additionally, scientific studies recommend improvements in Raman flow cell design and sample preconcentration methods to enhance sensitivity, particularly for nanoplastics [26]. Further refinements such as narrowband filtering and phase control of laser beams have been shown to significantly boost Raman imaging resolution and reliability [45].

4.2.1.6. Integrated and Multi-Modal Analytical Approaches

Given the compositional complexity and diversity of MNPs, single-method approaches are rarely sufficient. Integrated analytical strategies that combine spectroscopic, imaging, and thermal methods have gained traction for their ability to provide complementary information. Projects like LimnoPlast and LABPLAS recommend harmonized workflows that bring together FTIR, Raman, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and thermal degradation techniques to improve identification accuracy [44,46]. Likewise, recent studies advocate for combining chemical, optical, and chromatographic methods in modular workflows to enable comprehensive profiling of microplastics across varied matrices [34,47].

4.2.1.7. Addressing Instrumental Limitations and Background Noise

Instrumental background noise remains a major limitation for detecting trace levels of micro- and nanoplastics and their associated chemical signatures. AURORA has suggested measures such as implementing delay columns and establishing system decontamination protocols in LC-HRMS systems to reduce background interference without the need for full hardware replacement [38]. In parallel, broader research supports the development of advanced instrumentation to minimize signal interference, especially when detecting low-abundance plastic additives and degradation products in complex matrices [48].

4.2.1.8. Accurate Quantification and Mass Conversion

Quantifying micro- and nanoplastics in terms of mass, rather than particle count, is essential for environmental risk assessment and regulatory decision-making. However, this conversion is fraught with technical challenges. EUROqCHARM stresses the importance of validated calibration protocols to reliably transform particle counts into mass-based concentrations [49]. Additional literature supports the use of quantitative nuclear magnetic resonance (qNMR) methods to improve conversion accuracy, particularly in complex and heterogeneous samples [50].

4.2.1.9. Advanced Imaging for Biological Studies

Understanding how MNPs interact with biological tissues requires highly specialized imaging technologies. Techniques such as SEM, TEM, confocal microscopy, and fluorescence imaging are essential for visualizing particle uptake, localization, and potential effects [51,52]. Furthermore, dual-mode and in situ imaging methods are increasingly necessary to distinguish between internalized and surface-bound particles in biological systems [53,54]. Emerging approaches, such as MRI-based imaging and fluorescence lifetime imaging microscopy (FD-

FLIM), are expanding the toolkit for tracking nanoplastics at cellular resolution [55,56]. Applications for MRI, STED, and FD-FLIM for nanoplastics tracking in cells are emerging [55,56].

4.2.1.10. Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) Optimization

Atomic force microscopy (AFM) is a valuable tool for nanoscale characterization, but it requires further optimization for micro- and nanoplastics research. Improved nanomanipulation techniques are needed to attach nanoplastics to AFM probes for studies on adhesion and friction [57]. Enhancing probe geometry, particularly by using high aspect ratio tips with small radii, can significantly improve topographic and frictional resolution. Integration of nanomechanical and infrared spectroscopy within AFM platforms has also shown promise for label-free analysis of particle-cell interactions [54].

4.2.1.11. Microfluidic and Sensor Platforms

Emerging microfluidic and sensor-based systems offer promise for in situ detection of microplastics, but current devices still face limitations. Improvements are needed in detection thresholds particularly for particles below 5 μm as well as in manufacturing scalability and fluidic channel design [47,58]. Recent innovations include portable LSPR-based sensors and machine learning-enhanced holographic imaging systems, which combine high sensitivity with real-time data acquisition for environmental monitoring [59,60].

4.2.1.12. Instrument-Specific Hardware Improvements

Enhancing the capabilities of existing analytical hardware is crucial for advancing MNPs detection. Several improvements have been proposed, including increasing the penetration depth of ATR-FTIR, refining laser phase control, and using more durable and selective filter materials in Raman imaging and filtration setups [45,61]. These upgrades aim to improve the accuracy, resolution, and durability of key instrumentation across analytical workflows, currently missing from prevalent detection methods.

4.2.1.13. Portable Devices and Software for Real-Time Sensing

There is a growing demand for field-deployable and real-time sensing platforms. Portable amplifiers, imaging sensors, and software automation must be co-developed to enable reliable MNP detection on-site [58]. Tools like FLIM and confocal microscopy demand custom image analysis pipelines to enhance plastic segmentation and reduce background noise [47,62].

Taken together, these findings outline a deeply interlinked set of analytical needs spanning instrumentation, sample preparation, detection limits, imaging, data analysis, and method validation. The field demands both targeted technological refinement and holistic integration of analytical platforms to overcome the multifaceted challenges of MNPs research.

4.2.2. Standardization and Reference Materials

Reliable analysis of MNPs across environmental, biological, and technical matrices depends on robust standardization. This includes harmonized sampling, validated analytical procedures, standardized test materials, and reproducible reporting formats. Projects, agencies, and

scientific literature converge on this point, recognizing standardization as foundational for regulatory alignment, data comparability, and cross-study synthesis.

4.2.2.1. *Harmonized Methods and Protocols*

EU-funded projects such as AURORA, PlasticHeal, PlasticsFatE, and COST Action PRIORITY and ICPLASTIC consistently emphasize the need for harmonized protocols across sampling, detection, and analysis. AURORA proposes contamination control measures and enzymatic digestion workflows to maintain particle integrity during pre-processing [63]. PlasticHeal identifies variability in polymer identification and size classification across labs, urging adoption of unified methods [64].

At the regulatory level, ISO 24187:2023 [19] and ISO/TR 21960:2020 [21] offer standardized terminology and measurement guidelines, while the EC and EEA call for EU-wide analytical standards covering environmental, food, and biological matrices [5,13]. COST Action PRIORITY also stresses harmonized approaches for environmental sampling [65,66]. Similar concerns are echoed in literature [67–69].

Special attention is required for sampling and QA/QC protocols. Projects such as LimnoPlast, LABPLAS, and EUROqCHARM have developed standard operating procedures (SOPs) and quality assurance frameworks tailored to diverse environments, including freshwater and Arctic settings [46,70]. The literature supports standardized sampling approaches for air, soil, food, wastewater, and indoor matrices [42,71]. Detection in complex matrices such as human tissues, food, and wastewater remains challenging. EFSA, MONPLAS, and PlasticHeal call for matrix-specific protocols with improved digestion and particle recovery [9,24,72]. Additional studies identify the need for accurate detection in air, fish, indoor environments, and soils [30,73].

Efforts to improve methodological harmonization are increasingly focused on advanced tools. PlasticsFatE and PlasticHeal advocate for consistent exposure metrics and refined workflows across ecological and human health domains [21,74,75]. Recent developments include high-throughput omics platforms, ITS metabarcoding, PAM fluorometry, and tools to monitor immune and sub-lethal effects [76,77].

Industry groups additionally make a strong emphasis placed on harmonized EU definitions of recyclability, reuse, and recycled content calculation, alongside common EPR frameworks and reporting standards [78–80].

4.2.2.2. *Reference Materials and Realistic Models*

A critical barrier to methodological reliability is the lack of realistic, standardized MNP reference materials. Many studies currently rely on pristine polystyrene spheres, which do not reflect environmental aging or particle diversity. Projects such as PlasticsFatE, EUROqCHARM, PlasticHeal, and CUSP cluster of projects call for new materials generated through top-down degradation of consumer products [25,81].

These efforts include development of certified particles <50 µm [82], isotopically labelled materials, doped and surfactant-free models, and effervescent tablets for controlled exposure [81]. EUROqCHARM is producing size-fractionated particles via cryo-milling [83], and PlasticHeal has created protocols for labelled and unlabelled reference MNPs [44,83].

A stakeholder survey conducted by the JRC confirms the demand for centralized repositories, non-plastic control particles, customizable surface chemistries, and fluorescent tagging to support toxicological testing and exposure modelling [14].

4.2.2.3. *Regulatory Relevance and Remaining Gaps*

To support meaningful risk assessment and regulation, standardized data must directly inform policy. PlasticsFatE and CUSP highlight the integration of test outcomes into Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA), and advocate for defining minimum quality criteria for regulatory testing [84,85]. ECHA and the EC emphasize the importance of validated solubility, degradation, and dermal absorption tests to support regulatory decisions under Regulation (EU) 2023/2055, which restricts the placing of products containing intentionally added microplastics on the market [13,18].

Despite these advancements, critical technical gaps remain. Protocols for indoor air, reproductive tissues, and atmospheric matrices are still underdeveloped. Artificial aging techniques, micronization tools, and encapsulation systems are needed for exposure realism [86,87]. Calibration standards (e.g., for AFM, FT-IR), spectral libraries, and software tools like *siMPle* are essential for inter-instrument and inter-laboratory comparability [57,88,89].

Global harmonization remains a key priority. This includes alignment on terminology, mass quantification approaches (e.g., qNMR), contamination control workflows, and integration of metal-free manufacturing tools [90,91]. Without this level of coordination, cross-border comparison, regulatory coherence, and long-term trend analysis will remain limited.

Overall, standardization and the development of reference materials are foundational for advancing MNP science. Addressing the gaps identified above will enhance scientific coherence, support regulation, and enable meaningful comparisons across disciplines and geographies.

Parallely, industry highlights regulatory fragmentation, lack of technology-neutral rules, and absence of mirror clauses to ensure equivalent standards for imported recyclates [78,79,92].

4.2.3. **Data & Digital Tools**

Digital innovation plays a pivotal role in advancing MNPs research, particularly in areas of detection, exposure assessment, modelling, data integration, and public health monitoring. From AI-powered detection systems to unified data infrastructures, the application of smart technologies enables faster, more precise, and scalable solutions. Multiple EU-funded projects highlight critical gaps and technological needs in this space, spanning advanced analytics, machine learning, and harmonized digital platforms.

4.2.3.1. *Integrated Detection and Analytical Platforms*

Projects such as AURORA and Imptox call for advanced platforms capable of assessing combined effects of MNPs and co-contaminants. AURORA identifies a need for tools that integrate morphological and spectroscopic fingerprints of environmentally aged plastics using high-resolution methods like Photo-induced Force Microscopy (PiFM) [31]. Imptox demonstrates real-time airborne MNP detection using a combination of holography, fluorescence, and machine learning (Imptox). Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and other multivariate techniques are also deployed in PlasticHeal to evaluate particle uptake at the cellular level, reflecting a broader need for data-intensive analysis tools embedded within biological testing workflows [44].

4.2.3.2. AI and Machine Learning for Classification and Interpretation

Given the complexity of spectroscopic and imaging datasets, several initiatives advocate for AI-driven data interpretation. JPI Oceans is developing machine learning models for property-based similarity searches and rapid classification of microplastics, enabling automated analysis of large volumes of environmental data [93]. Further, AI-based tools integrating hyperspectral data and chemometric algorithms are being refined for faster, more reproducible results across laboratories, reducing human bias and enhancing scalability [94]. Recent scientific studies also emphasize the role of machine learning in enhancing spectral interpretation and chemical specificity in single-particle imaging [32,95].

4.2.3.3. Data Harmonization and Knowledge Integration

Fragmentation of MNP-related data across disciplines and sectors is a persistent barrier. POLYRISK and PlasticTrace emphasize the need for centralized repositories and interoperable databases combining regulatory, scientific, and industrial datasets [76,96]. Knowledge graphs and vector embedding technologies allow advanced search and link prediction even for substances lacking structural data, facilitating predictive toxicology and regulatory assessments. Similarly, ISO 24187:2023 and the EC's Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability advocate for standardized data processing protocols to support spectral interpretation and interlaboratory QA/QC [5,19].

Harmonized EU reporting systems and globally aligned definitions are presented as necessary to integrate data by the industry [78,79].

4.2.3.4. Digital Platforms for Policy and Ecosystem Integration

Tools such as the Marine Litter Assessment Tool (MALT) demonstrate how indicator-based digital systems can aggregate and visualize litter data across spatial scales, guiding targeted interventions [97]. FlexFunction2Sustain highlights the need for integrated digital infrastructures to link capabilities across Open Innovation Test Beds (OITBs), ensuring efficient SME access and long-term ecosystem sustainability [98].

Ellen MacArthur foundation and EuRic stress the importance of EPR reporting systems, deposit return tracking tools, and trade compliance platforms that are central governance infrastructures [92,99].

4.2.3.5. Behavioural and Socioeconomic Modelling Tools

Digital tools are not limited to physical particles. Projects such as PlastiSol explore integration of behaviour change frameworks into digital platforms to drive reductions in plastic use via targeted interventions [100]. Food Research International also underlines the value of consumer-focused data tools to evaluate willingness-to-pay for microplastic mitigation technologies, emphasizing the need for economic models tied to public perception and regulatory innovation [101].

Market modelling for EPR fee structures, competitiveness assessments, and import impact analysis are emphasized by the industry [92,99].

4.2.3.6. Advanced Modelling, Simulation and Bioinformatics Tools

In silico modelling is recognized as a cornerstone of predictive research on MNPs. Several studies call for improved computational tools to simulate nanoplastic-protein interactions [102], PET-enzyme degradation [103], and particle behaviour in turbulent aquatic environments [104,105]. These require both computational power and validated reference data. Bioinformatics tools are also needed to explore microbial responses to MNP exposure [73,106].

4.2.3.7. Statistical and Chemometric Support

The complexity of MNP datasets necessitates powerful statistical tools for analysing distributions, compositions, and transport behaviours. Improved parameterization of environmental transport models [107], better predictive QSPR models for sorption interactions [108], and molecular dynamics for fragmentation or bioavailability studies are repeatedly cited as essential [109]. Tools supporting reproducible contamination data analysis and ecological inference are also needed [74,110].

Digital and data-driven technologies are essential to manage the growing complexity of MNP detection, analysis, and regulation. As projects scale in ambition, the integration of smart systems, standardized datasets, and user-centric platforms will be critical to supporting science-based policy and protecting environmental and human health.

4.2.4. Exposure, Monitoring & Fate Analysis

Understanding the exposure pathways, environmental fate, and long-term dynamics of MNPs is fundamental for accurate risk assessment and regulatory decision-making. This section synthesizes technological needs derived from EU-funded projects and scientific literature, highlighting key priorities in human and environmental exposure monitoring, fate modelling, and data integration.

4.2.4.1. Monitoring Human and Environmental Exposure

Quantifying human exposure to MNPs remains hindered by inconsistent sampling protocols and a lack of sensitive detection methods. Projects such as AURORA and PlasticHeal highlight the need for improved models simulating degradation and transformation during digestion [31,64,111]. Imptox and CUSP call for robust tools to track long-term exposure through air, water, and food [84,112].

PlasticHeal also underscores the need for improved sampling systems for particles <10 µm in urban air and for continuous workplace monitoring systems [24]. POLYRISK emphasizes better cellular-level tracking and quantification of particle uptake [113].

In parallel, scientific literature confirms these challenges and adds specific technological gaps. For instance, sensitive analytical techniques are required to detect MNPs in biological matrices [114], and enhanced indoor air monitoring technologies must be developed to track MNP transport and resuspension [115].

4.2.4.2. Environmental Monitoring and Sampling Tools

Environmental monitoring is fragmented and lacks harmonization across compartments. EUROqCHARM has initiated standard protocols for sampling in diverse conditions including Arctic regions [68,116]. Papillons advocates for field-based exposure tests using aged plastics,

and LABPLAS highlights the need for validated soil sampling and toxicity characterization [117,118].

Projects such as PlasticsFatE and PlasticHeal recommend the development of harmonized sampling workflows, QA/QC protocols, and quality assurance [25,119]. JPI Oceans and MONPLAS also note the need for improved air sampling techniques and analytical tools in field and occupational settings [120,121].

Scientific evidence calls for deeper sampling of marine sediments (>1 meter) [122], improved WWTP effluent monitoring [123,124], and standardized airborne sampling methods [125]. Innovative approaches include the use of honeybees and inland birds as biosamplers [126,127].

4.2.4.3. Degradation, Fate, and Transport Modelling

Understanding MNP transformation and long-range transport is critical. PlasticsFatE and EC documents underscore the need for validated environmental models [7,128]. Projects like MicroplastiX simulate coastal particle transport, while DECOMPOSE develops polymers with programmed degradation.

Advanced models are needed to address aggregation, attachment, and atmospheric dispersion [127]. The ISO standards recommends lifecycle-based exposure models and harmonized fate assessment methods [20,21]. CUSP and ECHA reinforce the demand for models that trace nanoplastics through product lifecycles [17,84].

Literature expands this by calling for integration of hyporheic exchange models [129], sea-spray aerosolization mechanisms [124], and advanced washout coefficients for atmospheric modelling [130]. In terrestrial systems, catchment-specific models and tools for historical trend analysis are in demand [102,131].

4.2.4.4. Dosimetry and Biomonitoring for Exposure Quantification

Translating environmental concentrations to biologically meaningful doses is a key challenge. Projects like POLYRISK and PlasticHeal propose standardized dosimetry protocols and improved in vitro testing methods [109,111]. Human biomonitoring tools are also needed for clinical settings and cohort studies [111].

Scientific publications underscore the need for technologies to quantify nanoplastics in tissues and blood [112], and analytical tools to link ingestion with systemic distribution [132].

4.2.4.5. Chronic Exposure and Mixture Toxicity Models

Multiple projects address the complexity of chronic and combined exposures. PlasticHeal shows that MNPs can amplify toxic effects of other pollutants like arsenic and tobacco [121], and MONPLAS develops Adverse Outcome Pathway frameworks for linking cellular effects to exposure levels [133]. PlasticsFatE calls for dynamic exposure systems, stable exposure matrices, and models that account for aggregation and surface effects [25].

Further literature calls for better modelling of fiber release from textiles [134], fragmentation into nanoplastics [29], and microplastic behaviour in polar or deep-sea settings [135].

4.2.4.6. Agricultural and Ecosystem Impacts

Papillons and LABPLAS emphasize the importance of accounting for physicochemical variables in soil, such as pH and organic matter [115]. There is demand for data linking agricultural plastic use with food chain accumulation.

Scientific studies stress the need for in situ detection of plastics in plants using Raman spectroscopy [136], advanced tracking in food webs [137], and better monitoring in protected areas [138]. Field-based studies should also refine sampling for both terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems [139].

Together, these insights confirm that advancing the science of exposure and fate will require both cross-sectoral collaboration and technological breakthroughs in detection, modelling, and monitoring.

4.2.5. Ecotoxicology & Environment

The ecotoxicological and environmental health effects of MNPs remain significantly under characterized, particularly in terrestrial ecosystems such as agricultural soils. EU-funded research projects and peer-reviewed studies converge on key technological gaps, notably the need for realistic test materials, harmonized protocols, and advanced tools for ecosystem-level assessments. These are critical to understand risks to biodiversity, soil function, and environmental integrity.

4.2.5.1. Hazard Assessment Under Realistic Environmental Conditions

Projects such as Papillons and LABPLAS stress the need for test systems that replicate field conditions. Papillons calls for soil-specific protocols incorporating field-weathered plastics and parameters like pH and water retention [115] LABPLAS advocates integrating littering into LCIA tools to capture environmental impacts [116].

Scientific literature supports this with calls for in situ studies and field-based test systems, especially to assess uptake in macroinvertebrates and microbial responses in diverse soils [140,141]. Additional evidence underscores the need for experimental systems under natural field conditions to validate lab-based findings on plant responses [142,143].

4.2.5.2. Risks of Biodegradable Plastics and Additives

The assumption that biodegradable plastics are environmentally safe is questioned by LABPLAS and Momentum. LABPLAS recommends mandatory ecotoxicity testing of polymers and degradation products (LABPLAS - Supporting Biodegradables). Momentum emphasizes that microbial solutions like engineered consortia must undergo ecotoxicity evaluation prior to deployment [144].

Supporting studies reveal effects of biodegradable plastic mulches on soil microbial composition, greenhouse gas flux, and nutrient cycling [145,146]. Multi-omics platforms are urged for deeper functional insight [147]. LABPLAS further highlights the need for reliable testing and certification methods for biodegradability in marine and freshwater environments and for evaluating ecotoxicity of plastic additives and degradation fragments.

The industry strongly suggest certification frameworks are for bio-based plastics [148–150].

4.2.5.3. Monitoring of Impacts on Soil Health and Ecosystem Function

Soil ecosystem functionality is disrupted by plastic residues affecting structure, water retention, and microbial dynamics. Papillon proposes a risk matrix to classify agricultural plastics by microplastic release risk [151]. Reviews highlight the need for long-term, standardized assessment tools [152].

Further evidence links MNPs to altered nitrogen cycling, microbial assembly, and CO₂/N₂O emissions [153,154]. Plastic-induced changes in soil biochemical properties are still poorly understood and require systemic study. Tools for qualitative risk classification and standardized procedures for soil and food matrix spiking with MNPs are also needed [115].

4.2.5.4. Microbial and Pathogen-Related Risks

Imptox identifies the need to understand MNPs' role in transporting allergens, pathogens, and antibiotic resistance via plastisphere biofilms [112]. PlasticsFatE calls for studies across varied aquatic environments to examine temperature-dependent variations in horizontal gene transfer and its ecotoxicological implications [128].

4.2.5.5. Molecular and Organism-Level Responses

There is a pressing need to study physiological and immune responses in aquatic organisms. Advanced tools like PAM fluorometry and high-res imaging are needed to examine impacts on photosynthesis and neurotoxicity [155,156]. Leaf-to-root translocation and nanoplastic interactions in plants also require targeted exploration [51].

Molecular dynamics and docking simulations are recommended to model interactions between additives and biota [157]. Metabolomics and omics-based early biomarkers are increasingly vital for nanospecific toxicity assessments [158,159]. Improved understanding of sorption/desorption kinetics involving biofilms is also essential [160].

4.2.5.6. Combined Effects and Environmental Interactions

Interactions with co-pollutants like heavy metals are understudied. Combined stressors may exacerbate ecotoxicity and ecosystem disruption [161,162]. Tools to monitor leaching and sorption of additives are needed [159].

Advanced models must simulate uptake kinetics, trophic transfer, and behavioural variability in aquatic organisms [163,164]. New approaches are required to monitor fungal/bacterial colonization and links to antimicrobial resistance [77,165].

4.2.5.7. Agricultural Productivity and Ecosystem Resilience

Plastic residues may impair root architecture, micronutrient uptake, and water retention in crops. Tools are needed to study interactions with nanomaterials (e.g., MoO₃) and effects on productivity [166]. Imptox also notes dietary exposure risks from plant uptake of nanoplastics [112].

Vertical migration of particles, soil texture influences, and field-trial data are needed to validate models of agroecosystem response [167,168]. Studies call for technologies like SEM to support microplastic-soil interaction research [141].

This body of work confirms that effective environmental management of MNPs requires innovations in ecotoxicological design, exposure realism, and multi-scale environmental

modelling. Future technologies must bridge the gap between laboratory precision and environmental complexity to safeguard ecological integrity.

4.2.6. Human Health & Toxicology

The implications of MNPs for human health remain among the most urgent and least understood aspects of the plastics pollution crisis. Research to date has shown significant potential for these particles to cause physical and chemical harm through mechanisms such as inflammation, oxidative stress, and the delivery of toxic chemicals or pathogens. However, the field is hindered by major gaps in toxicological data, experimental modelling, and standardized health assessment tools. This section summarizes the technological and methodological needs required to improve our understanding of the toxicokinetics, bioactivity, and chronic effects of MNPs on human systems, as identified across EU-funded projects and regulatory bodies.

4.2.6.1. Toxicokinetic and Systemic Health Impacts

One of the central challenges in assessing human health risks from MNPs is the lack of data on their absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion (ADME). The EFSA has stressed the absence of reliable data on local gastrointestinal effects and systemic exposure routes.⁸ Similarly, PlasticsFatE calls for comprehensive studies on bioaccumulation and internal dose measurement in humans [169]. Understanding the translocation of particles across biological barriers such as the gut lining, blood-brain barrier, and placenta is also a key need. CUSP highlights a critical lack of tools to track MNP fate in the body, including bioaccumulation and long-term residence [84].

4.2.6.2. Development of Realistic and Ethical Toxicity Models

There is a widespread recognition that current *in vivo* toxicology models fail to reflect realistic human exposure conditions, such as low-dose, long-term, and mixed exposure scenarios. In response, multiple projects are developing alternative models:

- PlasticHeal identifies a need for new approach methodologies (NAMs) to simulate chronic exposure and transformation-induced toxicity [121].
- The CUSP cluster of projects similarly calls for long-term, low-dose exposure models that better mirror real-world conditions [170].
- MONPLAS reports that oversimplified cell models lack predictive value, and recommends high-content screening, organ-on-a-chip systems, and 3D cell cultures [133].

4.2.6.3. Advanced In Vitro and Omics-Based Tools

To enhance mechanistic understanding, the integration of omics platforms (e.g., transcriptomics, proteomics, metabolomics) into MNP toxicity studies is gaining traction. PlasticHeal highlights the application of kinome profiling and RNA-seq to detect early molecular events associated with MNPL exposure [121], while also developing proteomics protocols to study protein corona formation post-digestion [109]. *In vitro* models derived from human stem cells offer improved biological relevance, but face reproducibility and validation challenges. Further development is needed to enhance their regulatory acceptability [64].

4.2.6.4. Cellular and Molecular Toxicity Endpoints

Several methodological gaps remain in the assessment of cell-level responses to MNPs. The PlasticHeal consortium has developed and optimized a suite of advanced assays to improve genotoxicity and cytotoxicity testing:

- A higher-throughput comet assay using GelBond films for efficient DNA damage screening [171].
- Cell sorting protocols to isolate MNPs-internalized cells, improving assay specificity.
- Improved LDH release assays and mitochondrial membrane potential measurements tailored for MNPLs.

These refinements are critical to avoid interference by MNPs' physical properties and increase assay reliability.

4.2.6.5. Health Impacts of Weathered and Realistic MNPs

Most current toxicological studies use pristine plastic particles, which do not reflect environmental conditions. The CUSP cluster of projects stress the importance of simulating weathered, heterogeneous particles, which have altered surface chemistry and greater bioavailability of toxic components [84,113]. POLYRISK also advocates for the development of models that assess health impacts from airborne plastics, including inhalation and skin irritability testing, pointing to gaps in dermal toxicity data [172].

4.2.6.6. MNPs as Vectors for Contaminants and Pathogens

A major emerging concern is the role of MNPs as carriers for harmful chemicals, pathogens, or antibiotic resistance genes. Both Momentum and CUSP identify the need for in-depth research into the "plastisphere" biofilms forming on plastic particles that may carry allergens or pathogenic organisms [170,173].

These biological interfaces may enhance MNP toxicity and immune interactions, yet remain poorly understood. Mechanistic tools are required to explore their behaviour in vivo and during digestion.

4.2.6.7. Extended Toxicological Targets and Systems Biology

Recent studies have emphasized a broader range of toxicological endpoints, including neurotoxicity, endocrine disruption, immunotoxicity, and metabolic disorders. Advanced models are needed to simulate the molecular and cellular mechanisms involved:

- Development of metabolomic platforms to assess mitochondrial damage and metabolic effects [174,175].
- Omics-based methods and biomarkers to evaluate impacts on the intestinal barrier, brain function, and foetal development [176,177].
- Models to understand chronic effects of MNP exposure on allergy development and hormone regulation [178].

Integrative systems biology approach is increasingly being recognized as necessary to understand the cumulative and multifaceted health effects of MNPs, including their interactions with biological systems at molecular, cellular, and systemic levels. recognized as necessary to capture the complex, cumulative health effects of MNPs. Together, the findings across projects and studies underscore a shared urgency to develop predictive, ethically sustainable, and

mechanistically robust models of MNPs toxicity. Addressing these technological gaps is not only essential to improve scientific understanding but also to support risk assessment frameworks and regulatory decision-making for public health protection.

4.2.7. Regulation, Policy & Risk Assessment

Effective regulation and risk assessment of MNPs require frameworks that reflect real-world exposure scenarios, address mixture toxicity, and accommodate the uncertainties surrounding MNPs behaviours and lifecycle impacts. Numerous EU-funded projects and scientific studies recommend the pressing need to modernize legal instruments, risk assessment methodologies, and circular economy policies to match the complexity of MNPs-related risks.

4.2.7.1. Gaps in Regulatory Frameworks and Mixture Assessment

The EC's Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability and EuRic highlights systemic regulatory deficiencies, such as the absence of Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) criteria for polymers [5,80]. Projects like PlasticHeal and PlasticsFatE advocate for integrating SSbD principles into plastic design and enhancing control mechanisms over pellet loss and fragmentation during manufacturing and transport [5,74]. Additionally, REACH lacks effective mixture assessment factors, which hinders the regulation of combined exposures to MNPs and other pollutants. Current frameworks also fail to address the lifecycle complexity of synthetic polymers, especially in soil and agricultural contexts. The industry calls therefore for coherent EU rules and technology-neutral calculation methods for recycled content [78,80].

4.2.7.2. Risk Assessment Tools Tailored to MNPs

PlasticsFatE emphasizes the need for bespoke risk assessment tools that consider particle-specific properties such as bioaccumulation, surface reactivity, and interactions with co-contaminants [179,180]. These tools must extend beyond traditional chemical risk models and accommodate secondary nanoplastics-aged, fragmented particles with unpredictable behaviours [7]. ISO/TR 13121 recommends assumption-based and iterative risk modelling approaches under conditions of high uncertainty. Projects support dynamic risk profiles and adaptive risk assessment methodologies, especially those accounting for cumulative exposure across a product's lifecycle [20].

4.2.7.3. Policy Integration for Circularity and Sustainable Design

PlasticHeal and the European Environment Agency advocate for embedding circularity into regulatory design principles, particularly by incentivizing recyclable polymers, reducing hazardous additives, and incorporating reuse strategies [11,74].

EuRic points out the lack of alignment of SUPD, PPWR, EPR, and Green Deal objectives [92]. Projects like Papillons and LABPLAS highlight the need for ecotoxicity-informed product design in agricultural plastics, proposing minimum reporting standards and environmental risk matrices [118]. Moreover, LCA models should explicitly account for environmental littering to better quantify plastic pollution burdens [122].

4.2.7.4. Standardization in Regulatory Testing and Thresholds

Multiple initiatives point to a lack of validated and harmonized testing protocols for MNP toxicity, bioaccumulation, and environmental persistence. The PlasticsFatE project urges the revision of OECD guidelines and the introduction of new quality criteria for MNP studies [25]. Standardization is particularly critical for comparability across EU Member States. The Papillons project highlights the importance of certified reference materials and uniform sampling procedures, particularly for soil contamination studies [117]. PlasticTrace promote metrological traceability and SI-aligned quantification strategies for diverse matrices [81].

4.2.7.5. Economic and Market Instruments for Risk Mitigation

Some studies explore economic levers for reducing MNP exposure risks. For instance, seafood certification schemes that reflect MNP depuration efficiency could incentivize safer consumer choices [101].

Papillons proposes agricultural risk classification tools to rank products based on their environmental plastic pollution potential [151]. Market instruments such as eco-labels and producer responsibility schemes could further support regulatory compliance and encourage innovation in low-risk material design.

EPR fee modulation, recycled content targets, and infrastructure financing mechanisms are prioritized by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation, Plastics Europe and EuRic [92,99,181].

4.2.7.6. Integration into International Standards and Policy Instruments

PlasticTrace and CUSP stress the need to translate project findings into binding EU legislation and ISO/CEN standards. This includes defining regulatory exposure thresholds, certifying low-MNP products, and updating food safety and environmental protection directives [170]. POLYRISK is also developing domain-specific databases and regulatory informatics tools to support evidence-based policymaking [96].

Global alignment through Plastics Pact initiatives and mirror clauses for imports are proposed [79].

4.2.7.7. Monitoring, Infrastructure and Enforcement Technologies

The literature highlights the urgent need for robust plastic waste monitoring systems, particularly in wastewater treatment plants and agricultural soils. Improved sampling protocols, better waste segregation infrastructure, and innovative remediation technologies are critical to reducing environmental MNP loads [182,183].

Technological upgrades are also needed in regulatory surveillance of food packaging, drinking water, and consumer products [184,185]. Further, lifecycle-based regulatory models must account for atmospheric MNPs and their translocation in sensitive populations [186,187].

4.2.7.8. Advanced Modelling and Decision Support Tools

LCA and risk modelling platforms need to incorporate updated fate models, bioavailability data, and mixture toxicity factors. Studies stress the inadequacy of abundance-based indicators and call for models that integrate toxicokinetics and long-term ecological effects [188,189]. Integrating multi-source data and uncertainty into decision support systems is critical. High-throughput chemical screening and molecular databases should be aligned with regulatory requirements to identify harmful additives and prevent regrettable substitutions [190].

Addressing the regulatory and policy challenges posed by MNPs requires a multifaceted strategy. Scientific and project-based evidence points to major deficiencies in regulatory infrastructure, standardization, monitoring, and decision-making tools. Moving forward, cross-sectoral coordination, technology innovation, and regulatory harmonization are essential to ensuring effective risk governance and public protection from MNP pollution.

Lifecycle-based pathway comparison tools are proposed by the industry to prioritise environmentally preferable recycling routes [148]

4.2.8. Circular Economy, Sustainability & Safe-by-Design

One of the most effective ways to mitigate MNP pollution is through the redesign of plastic materials themselves. Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD), sustainable innovation, and advanced recycling strategies are essential to prevent plastic leakage into the environment, improve end-of-life treatment, and reduce toxicity. This section outlines the technological needs for biodegradable alternatives, improved recyclability, functional design, and environmentally benign materials as identified across European research projects and policy frameworks. While some of these innovations are already under development or in limited use, many remain emerging or recommended directions requiring further research, validation, and policy support.

4.2.8.1. Development of Sustainable and Biodegradable Alternatives

The transition to sustainable polymers is a cornerstone of MNP prevention. The COST Action PRIORITY emphasizes designing plastics that are more biodegradable and environmentally benign to replace conventional persistent polymers [94]. The EEA similarly highlights the need for biodegradable alternatives to agricultural mulch films, supported by real-world soil-safe degradation profiles [10].

The Papillons project notes that current "biodegradable" agricultural plastics may still generate MNPs in field conditions, and calls for verified, soil-safe product development (Papillons - Agricultural plastics and soil pollution) [151]. In packaging, FlexFunction2Sustain reports marine-biodegradable sachets achieving >70% degradation under seawater conditions [191]. DECOMPOSE contributes by developing metallo-supramolecular polymers with rapid aqueous degradation [192].

Sustainability certification and traceability for newly produced bio-based plastics is requested by the industry [149,150].

4.2.8.2. Safe-by-Design and Functional Innovation

SSbD strategies should incorporate degradation behaviour as a core criterion. ECHA emphasizes including biodegradability in nanomaterial design [18]. PlasticsFatE recommends using early-stage hazard indicators to guide innovation [193]. PlasticHeal is developing surface-functionalized MNPLs and improving PET/PLA emulsion stability for research use [194].

4.2.8.3. Recycling, Reprocessing, and Circular Economy Integration

While the industry is placing the large-scale expansion of collection, sorting, and recycling infrastructure as a priority [181,195], recycling remains challenged by contamination and material complexity. The EC's Chemicals Strategy calls for decontamination tech to recover

legacy-laden plastics. The EEA supports mechanical and chemical innovations, such as mono-material polypropylene laminates [191], while promoting cascade NIR sorting technologies. The EEA also stresses additive simplification to enhance recyclability and mass-balance systems for tracking recycled content [16].

4.2.8.4. Reducing Unintentional Emissions via Product Design

Product-level strategies are needed to curb emissions. The EC proposes eco-design standards for textiles, tyres, paints, and artificial turf [5]. EEA advocates the following [13]:

- **Textiles:** Fiber selection, coating, and weave modifications reduce wash-off
- **Tyres:** Abrasion-resistant designs and vehicle adjustments.
- **Paints:** Low-shedding coatings and safe removal practices.
- **Artificial Turf:** Alternative infill materials and containment systems.

4.2.8.5. Biotechnology and Plastic Degradation

Biodegradation via engineered microbes offers promise. Momentum highlights microbial engineering for efficient PE and PP degradation [144]. Strategies include pre-treatment (UV/oxidation), enzyme enhancement (PETases/laccases), and microbial consortia. Detection tools to track degradation intermediates are also needed.

4.2.8.6. Labelling, Traceability, and Consumer Communication

Misinformation on "bioplastics" undermines effective disposal. EEA and EC but also FoodDrinkEurope and EuRic call for standardized labelling systems and QR-coded disposal guidance [78,80,196]. Mass-balance verification and life cycle assessment tools would be necessary to validate biodegradability and recycled content [11].

4.2.8.7. Food System Applications and Intelligent Materials

The food system is a key domain for SSbD innovation. EEA supports intelligent packaging and nano-sensors for spoilage monitoring [12]. Food Research International points to gaps in seafood depuration methods and recommends improved treatment technologies [101].

4.2.8.8. Advancements in Wastewater Treatment and Capture

Improved wastewater filtration and treatment processes are necessary to capture smaller micro- and nanoplastics [115]. Some identified needs include:

- Enhanced filters for domestic appliances, which are available but not yet widely adopted or standardized [197];
- WWTPs upgrades: such as improved sludge management, ozonation, and advanced tertiary treatments, which are used in certain facilities but are not yet commonly applied or specifically optimized for micro- and nanoplastic removal [132].

4.2.8.9. Material Engineering and Composite Innovation

Bioplastics need improved properties for broader adoption. Areas for development include:

- Mechanical strength and thermal stability [198].
- PLA/PBAT/PPC blends for packaging films [199].
- Compatibilizers and nanofillers [200].

4.2.8.10. *Enzymatic and Photocatalytic Degradation Pathways*

Enzyme engineering is advancing the biodegradation of PET, with improved PETases and cutinases showing greater efficiency and stability under environmental conditions [103]. In parallel, photocatalysis using visible light—particularly with defect-engineered ZnO on glass fiber substrates—enhances the mineralization of persistent plastics [201]. These emerging approaches offer promising, low-impact alternatives to conventional plastic degradation methods.

4.2.8.11. *Agricultural Applications and Mulching Films*

Biodegradable films must be adapted to soil and climate conditions. Risks include additive leaching and persistence [202]. Monitoring weathering effects and degradation is critical [203].

4.2.8.12. *Environmental Remediation and Recovery Technologies*

Magnetic nanomaterials like M-CNTs show potential for MNP and contaminant removal [204]. Constructed wetlands and WWTP infrastructure engineering can increase capture rates [182].

4.2.8.13. *Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) in Food and Agriculture*

Studies promote MoO₃-based nanofertilizers and CuO-cellulose packaging, with toxicity management [166]. Computational design and green chemistry are essential for next-generation additives [158]. Achieving sustainable plastic design requires a convergence of biotechnology, material science, and systems-level innovation. Safe-by-Design must become a guiding principle across product lifecycles from molecular engineering to recycling to support a circular economy and minimize MNP risks [78,149].

4.3. Quantitative analysis

4.3.1. Thematic focused analysis

The insights presented across the above-mentioned subsections (thematic sub-groups) outline key technological directions and highlight areas where further innovation, validation, and implementation are still needed. The Figure 4 provides a quantitative synthesis of the technological needs related to MNPs identified through the systematic literature review and EU project analysis. The figure displays the distribution of extracted needs across thematic groups and more detailed sub-groups, with bars representing the frequency with which each need appears in literature. This provides a detailed overview of the needs landscape within each broad thematic group.

Table 5 provides additionally a summary of leading sub-thematics by thematic groups in terms of needs.

Regarding the *Analytical Methods & Detection Technologies* theme, the most often cited needs belong to Detection of smaller particles and improved sensitivity (see 4.2.1.1) and Optimization of sample preparation and digestion protocols (see 4.2.1.4). Their prominence reflects a shared recognition that current analytical workflows still struggle to reliably detect nanoplastics and very small microplastics in complex matrices.

Within the *Standardization and Reference Materials* theme, Harmonized methods and protocols (see 4.2.2.1) emerge as the priority, followed by Reference materials and realistic models (see 4.2.2.2). This pattern highlights that the absence of harmonized analytical and sampling procedures remains a major obstacle and a priority to data comparability and regulatory uptake. The strong emphasis on realistic reference materials further indicates that reliance on pristine, idealized particles is no longer considered sufficient to support environmentally and biologically relevant assessments.

In the *Exposure, Monitoring & Fate Analysis* thematic group, the most frequently cited needs belong to Environmental monitoring and sampling tools (see 4.2.4.2) and Degradation, fate, and transport modelling (see 4.2.4.3). This reflects a demand for robust tools (sampling tool and analytical tools) to quantify MNP occurrence across environmental compartments, coupled with the need to understand how particles transform, migrate, and persist over time. It underlines that exposure assessment should increasingly be framed as a dynamic, system-level challenge rather than a static measurement problem.

For *Ecotoxicology & Environment*, the leading sub-groups are Hazard assessment under realistic environmental conditions (see 4.2.5.1) and Monitoring of impacts on soil health and ecosystem function (4.2.5.3). Their prominence signals a shift away from simplified laboratory tests toward more ecologically relevant approaches that capture field conditions, aged particles, and long-term ecosystem responses. The strong focus on soils and ecosystem functions also reflects increasing concern about terrestrial impacts, which have been underrepresented compared to aquatic systems until now.

Regarding *Human Health & Toxicology*, the two most often cited needs belong to Toxicokinetic and systemic health impacts (see 4.2.6.1) and Advanced in vitro and omics-based tools (see 4.2.6.3) sub-group. This points to the identified challenge of understanding how MNPs are absorbed, distributed, and retained in the human body, while also developing mechanistically informative and ethically acceptable models to study their effects. The prominence of omics-based tools indicates a move toward systems-level and pathway-oriented toxicology rather than reliance on traditional endpoints alone.

For *Regulation, Policy & Risk Assessment*, Standardization in regulatory testing and thresholds (see 4.2.7.4) and Risk assessment tools tailored to MNPs (see 4.2.7.2) stand out as the top sub-categories. This reflects a strong consensus that existing regulatory frameworks are not well adapted to particle-based stressors such as MNPs. The emphasis on tailored risk assessment tools indicates the need to move beyond classical chemical risk paradigms toward approaches that account for particle size, shape, surface properties, and mixture effects.

Regarding *Data & Digital Tools*, the most prominent cited needs fall within Advanced modelling, simulation and bioinformatics tools (see 4.2.3.6) and AI and machine learning for classification and interpretation (see 4.2.3.2) sub-group. Their dominance highlights the growing complexity and volume of MNP-related data, which increasingly requires computational approaches for integration, pattern recognition, and predictive analysis. These needs also reflect a transition toward more automated, scalable, and reproducible analytical and interpretative pipelines.

Finally, in the *Circular Economy, Sustainability & Safe-by-Design* thematic group, the leading thematic sub-groups are Development of sustainable and biodegradable alternatives (see 4.2.8.1) and Advancements in wastewater treatment and capture (see 4.2.8.8). These identified

needs illustrate the current limits on mitigation strategies, preventive perspectives and MNP monitoring.

Table 5 : Leading sub-thematics by thematic groups in terms of needs

Thematic Group	Leading Sub-thematics
Analytical Methods & Detection Technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detection of smaller particles and improved sensitivity • Optimization of sample preparation and digestion protocols
Standardization and Reference Materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Harmonized methods and protocols • Reference materials and realistic models
Exposure, Monitoring & Fate Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental monitoring and sampling tools • Degradation, fate, and transport modelling
Ecotoxicology & Environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hazard assessment under realistic environmental conditions • Monitoring of impacts on soil health and ecosystem function
Human Health & Toxicology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Toxicokinetic and systemic health impacts • Advanced in vitro and omics-based tools
Regulation, Policy & Risk Assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardization in regulatory testing and thresholds • Risk assessment tools tailored to MNPs
Data & Digital Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced modelling, simulation and bioinformatics tools • AI and machine learning for classification and interpretation
Circular Economy, Sustainability & Safe-by-Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of sustainable and biodegradable alternatives • Advancements in wastewater treatment and capture

Figure 4 : Quantification of cited technology needs by thematic groups and sub-groups

4.3.2. Domain focused analysis

Figure 5 provides a quantitative synthesis of the technological needs split by domain and Table 6 presents a summary of the leading sub-thematics by domain.

In cross-Domain studies, the larger share of extracted needs falls into Harmonized Methods and Protocols (see 4.2.2.1). Needs related to Advanced Spectroscopic and Imaging Techniques (see 4.2.1.2), Optimization of Sample Preparation and Digestion Protocols (see 4.2.1.4) and Detection of Smaller Particles and Improved Sensitivity (see 4.2.1.1) also represent a high proportion of cross-domain needs. Reference Materials and Realistic Models (see 4.2.2.2) are equally prominent requests. Development of Sustainable and Biodegradable Alternatives (see 4.2.8.1), needs related to Degradation, Fate, and Transport Modelling (see 4.2.4.3) and Environmental Monitoring and Sampling Tools (see 4.2.4.2) are also repeatedly cited. Additional cross-domain needs concern the improvement of AI and Machine Learning for Classification (see 4.2.3.2).

Regarding the Environment domain, Environmental Monitoring and Sampling Tools (see 4.2.4.2) type of needs and Harmonized Methods and Protocols (see 4.2.2.1) seem to represent the highest priority. Needs related to Degradation, Fate, and Transport Modelling (see 4.2.4.3), as well as Detection of Smaller Particles and Improved Sensitivity (see 4.2.1.1), are also often found in literature. A further notable portion of needs falls into Advancements in Wastewater Treatment and Capture (see 4.2.8.8). Monitoring of Impacts on Soil Health and Ecosystem Function (see 4.2.5.3), Advanced Modelling, Simulation and Bioinformatics Tools (see 4.2.3.6), Policy Integration for Circularity and Sustainable Design (see 4.2.7.3), and Advanced In Vitro and Omics-Based Tools (see 4.2.6.3) are also identified as thematics for further development or improvement.

Within Food-related studies, Monitoring Human and Environmental Exposure (see 4.2.4.1) represent the most often cited type of need. Several other analytical or standardization thematics including Detection of Smaller Particles and Improved Sensitivity (see 4.2.1.1), Optimization of Sample Preparation and Digestion Protocols (see 4.2.1.4), and Harmonized Methods and Protocols (see 4.2.2.1) are also usually stated. Development of Sustainable and Biodegradable Alternatives (see 4.2.8.1), along with Environmental Monitoring and Sampling Tools improvements (see 4.2.4.2) equally dominate the food-related needs. Other needs address Risk Assessment Tools Tailored to MNPs (see 4.2.7.2), improvement of our understanding of MNPs as Vectors for Contaminants and Pathogens (see 4.2.6.6), Toxicokinetic and Systemic Health Impacts (see 4.2.6.1), Combined Effects and Environmental Interactions (see 4.2.5.6), and Integrated Detection and Analytical Platforms (see 4.2.3.1).

In the Health domain, the largest share of extracted needs belongs to Toxicokinetic and Systemic Health Impacts (see 4.2.6.1). Detection of Smaller Particles and Improved Sensitivity (see 4.2.1.1) and Advanced Imaging for Biological Studies (see 4.2.1.9) seems to represent recurrent requests. Needs related to Advanced Modelling, Simulation and Bioinformatics Tools (see 4.2.3.6) and Monitoring Human and Environmental Exposure (see 4.2.4.1) also represent notable proportions. Harmonized Methods and Protocols (see 4.2.2.1), Molecular and

Organism-Level Responses (see 4.2.5.5), Standardization in Regulatory Testing and Thresholds (see 4.2.7.4) and Safe-by-Design and Functional Innovation (see 4.2.8.2) are also health related demands.

Table 6 : Leading sub-thematics by domain

Domain	Leading Sub-thematics
Cross-Domain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Harmonized Methods and Protocols • Advanced Spectroscopic and Imaging Techniques • Optimization of Sample Preparation and Digestion Protocols • Detection of Smaller Particles and Improved Sensitivity • Reference Materials and Realistic Models • Development of Sustainable and Biodegradable Alternatives
Environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental Monitoring and Sampling Tools • Harmonized Methods and Protocols • Degradation, Fate, and Transport Modelling • Detection of Smaller Particles and Improved Sensitivity • Advancements in Wastewater Treatment and Capture • Monitoring of Impacts on Soil Health and Ecosystem Function
Food	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitoring Human and Environmental Exposure • Detection of Smaller Particles and Improved Sensitivity • Optimization of Sample Preparation and Digestion Protocols • Harmonized Methods and Protocols • Development of Sustainable and Biodegradable Alternatives • Environmental Monitoring and Sampling Tools
Health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Toxicokinetic and Systemic Health Impacts • Detection of Smaller Particles and Improved Sensitivity • Advanced Imaging for Biological Studies • Advanced Modelling, Simulation and Bioinformatics Tools • Monitoring Human and Environmental Exposure • Harmonized Methods and Protocols

Figure 5 : Quantification of cited technology needs by domain

5. Integration with downstream WP

The desk research analysis relies on the explicit statement of needs and limitations within the articles and project documents, intrinsically constrained by the composition of the underlying corpus. Consequently, the frequency with which a given need is identified reflects how often it is reported, rather than its absolute importance. Needs that are well recognized and repeatedly discussed in the literature may therefore appear overrepresented, while equally critical but less explicitly articulated gaps may be underrepresented. Additionally, although the use of automated extraction and classification combined with expert validation improves consistency and scalability, it cannot fully eliminate interpretive subjectivity. The framing of needs within articles, the level of detail provided by authors, and disciplinary differences in terminology can all influence how needs are expressed and subsequently grouped. Taken together, these limitations indicate that the quantified distribution of needs should be interpreted as a structured representation of explicitly articulated technological gaps within the current research and policy landscape and might overlook certain MNP-related challenges. This reinforces the importance of complementing this already strong desk research foundation with expert consultation, stakeholder engagement, and forward-looking gap analysis, as implemented in parallel or subsequent or project tasks, including WP6.

Figure 6 specifically provides an integrative synthesis linking the thematic groups identified through the literature-driven approach (left-hand side) to the priority needs emerged from the co-creation and gap analysis process presented in D6.1 (right-hand side). It visually demonstrates how the two work packages complement each other, are conceptually aligned and that D6.1 is a direct aggregation of multiple, consistently recurring technological bottlenecks highlighted in the present deliverable. Note that, needs originating from *Analytical Methods & Detection Technologies* and *Standardization and Reference Materials* converge strongly toward the priority need of *access to infrastructure and advanced analytical capabilities*, as well as *standardization of protocols* and to a lesser extent to *Cross-sectoral data integration*. Similarly, thematic groups related to *Exposure, Monitoring & Fate Analysis* directly links to *Environmental fate and degradation, Regulatory, Policy & Risk assessment to Traceability and authenticity monitoring*, and *Data & digital tools* to *Cross-sectoral data integration*. *Human Health & Toxicology*, and *Ecotoxicology & Environment* as well as *Circular economy, sustainability and SSD* jointly feed into priorities such as *human exposure modelling, environmental fate and degradation, risk assessment*, and *One Health assessment and Sustainable and function food packaging*.

Figure 6 : Integrative synthesis linking D5.2 and D6.1 identified needs

6. Conclusions

D5.2 comprehensively identifies and quantifies the diverse technological needs emerging from contemporary research and policy recommendations on MNPs, in line with the key selected priorities defined in WP4. The evidence collected demonstrates that progress in this field depends on overcoming several interconnected scientific and infrastructural limitations.

The thematic analysis highlighted key priority areas for advancing research and management of micro- and nanoplastics. Major needs include improved **detection of smaller particles**, **optimized analytical workflows**, and the **development of harmonized methods and realistic reference materials** to ensure data comparability. Strong emphasis has also been placed on **environmental monitoring and modelling** of particle fate, as well as more ecologically relevant impact assessments. In human health, understanding toxicokinetics and leveraging **advanced in vitro and omics approaches** are critical. Regulatory progress requires **MNP-specific risk assessment frameworks** and standardized thresholds, while growing data complexity calls for **advanced modelling and AI-based tools**. Finally, the development of sustainable alternatives and **improved wastewater treatment solutions** remains essential for effective mitigation and prevention.

Across domains, a central bottleneck remains in the **detection and characterization**, especially for nanoplastics. Despite methodological advances, the ability to reliably identify nanoparticles, especially in complex biological and environmental matrices, is still limited. Both EU-funded projects and the scientific literature referred for this work, repeatedly highlight the need for integrated spectroscopic, thermal, and imaging techniques, underscoring that this is not a niche gap but a shared and foundational priority across research domains.

Closely tied to this issue is the persistent **lack of standardization**. harmonized protocols, reference materials, and QA/QC frameworks are essential to ensure comparability across studies and laboratories. While European initiatives have made significant strides in developing SOPs and interlaboratory tools, the scientific literature indicates unresolved challenges in applying these across complex matrices, such as food, sludge, and biological samples. This reinforces the importance of aligning project-based innovations with broader validation and implementation efforts.

The **growing volume of data** ranging from toxicological results to environmental measurements add further complexity. In both policy-facing and research contexts, digital tools such as machine learning, data harmonization platforms, and computational modelling are increasingly critical. However, the literature often emphasizes the technical depth of these tools, while EU projects and documents focus more on their interoperability and usability for regulatory and societal applications. Bridging these two perspectives will be essential for building scalable, applied solutions.

In the domain of **health impact assessment**, there is broad agreement across sources that existing models are insufficient to simulate realistic, chronic, low-dose exposures. Literature reviews stress the limitations of current toxicological assays, particularly regarding cellular

uptake, long-term effects, and mixture toxicity. EU projects complement this by actively developing novel *in vitro* systems and omics-based endpoints, highlighting a productive convergence between methodological critique and innovation.

Material design and biodegradability emerge more strongly from project activities (showcased by the project output) and industry groups than from the academic literature, reflecting the role of R&D in driving applied innovation. While the literature identifies the limitations of current degradation testing and environmental relevance, EU projects propose targeted advances in polymer chemistry, biodegradation certification, and SSbD frameworks.

Collectively, these findings suggest that advancing research on MNPs requires a systemic approach. Method development, standardization, health impact assessment, digital infrastructure, and material innovation must evolve in parallel. The comparative analysis of project outputs and literature confirms both a shared understanding of core technological gaps and complementary strengths in their respective approaches to addressing them.

This deliverable constitutes an evidence-based foundation for gap analysis and prioritisation activities. By systematically consolidating technological needs across thematic categories and sub-categories, it provides the necessary granularity to inform the co-creation-driven prioritisation process undertaken in WP6 and subsequent work packages.

Overall, FHERITALE, through this deliverable, contributes to that effort by mapping the current landscape and identifying key technological directions for future action.

7. Supplementary material

Supplementary material can be found on Zenodo:

- Vankoningsloo, M.; Renier, N.; Sharma, S.; Mustatea, G.; Van Loco, J. FHERITALE - **List of Technology Needs Related to Micro and Nanoplastic Research** 2026. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19365901>

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